

HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF E-GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITES MODIFIED WITH NH₂-MWCNT

M.M. Rahman¹, M. Hosur^{2*}, S. Zainuddin², S. Jeelani²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, USA,

² Department of Material Science and Engineering, Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, USA

* Corresponding author (hosur@mytu.tuskegee.edu)

Keywords: *High velocity impact, Carbon nanotubes, Calendaring method, Absorbed energy*

1. Introduction

Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) matrix composites are increasingly used as alternatives to conventional metallic materials in various armored structures of military vehicles due to their light weight, high stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight. FRP composites are preferred over conventional materials in the battlefield for light weight feature as this material class increases the mobility of vehicles to avoid enemy threats. However, impact resistance is one of the major concerns for fiber reinforced composite due to its high susceptibility to impact damage. Glass fiber has been attractive material as reinforcement in composites due to low cost, high impact strength, high chemical resistance and excellent insulating properties. Because of good stiffness, strength, excellent chemical resistance, dimensional stability, and excellent adhesion with fillers and fibers, epoxy has been excellent candidate in glass fiber reinforced composites among polymer matrix. Typically, glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites are considered as high-ductility advanced composites which are capable of absorbing maximum projectile's kinetic energy, but have limited ability against deforming or fracturing due to impact by projectile [1]. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have high potential to combine the benefits of higher absorption capability as well as high hardness. They exhibit an exceptionally high aspect ratio in combination with low density, high strength, stiffness and hardness, which makes them

potential candidate for the reinforcement of polymer-based composite materials. As a result, carbon nanotubes reinforced polymer matrix composites might be highly effective as armor structures while high strength combined with high ductility might absorb more kinetic energy of the projectile without much deformation. High surface area of CNTs provides desirable interfaces for stress transfer effectively in composite material. Ajayan et al. investigated stress transfer mechanism in CNT/epoxy composites [2]. They found multi-walled carbon nanotubes comparatively more efficient during stress transfer from matrix to CNTs than single-walled nanotubes. On the contrary, another study found that this high surface area induces undesirable strong attractive forces between CNTs which leads to excessive agglomeration [3]. Various dispersion methods to de-agglomerate nanotubes in polymer resins, such as stirring, sonication and high shear mixing have been reported in literature [4-6].

Besides, the interfacial adhesion between CNTs and matrix was reported to improve by functionalizing the CNTs. Tailored amino, carboxyl or glycidyl groups enable covalent bonding between CNTs and epoxy resulting in improved interfacial bonding. The positive effects of functionalized CNTs on the mechanical properties are reported by various researchers [7-9]. In our recent study, a combined dispersion of 0.3 wt. % NH₂-MWCNTs by sonication and calendaring method lead to an optimum improvement in

terms of flexure and thermo-mechanical properties [5].

So far, most of the studies were about determining how the failure mechanism and penetration phenomenon occur during ballistic impacts through theoretical and numerical predictions [10-14]. Very few studies have been conducted on the control of damage behavior and mechanism of high velocity impact properties of FRP composites using nanoparticles. Javad et al. carried out high velocity impact test of nanoclay reinforced unsaturated polyester (UP) resin and better performance was found for samples containing 1.5 wt. % nanoclay [15]. Avila et al. focused on high velocity impact of two hybrid nanocomposites i.e. glass fiber/epoxy/nanoclay and glass fiber/epoxy/nanographite [16]. The addition of nanoclay and nanographite to glass fiber/epoxy laminates increased the impact resistance. Besides, they found a considerable effect of using nanoparticles on the failure mechanisms of glass fiber/epoxy composites. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no studies reported in the open literature on the effect of NH₂-MWCNTs on the ballistic response of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites. Hence, in this study, the effect of amino-functionalized MWCNTs on the ballistic impact properties of E-glass/epoxy composite laminates was investigated. Composite samples for ballistic test were fabricated using hot press process. Samples of 120 x 120 x 5.25 mm were subjected to ballistic impact using a gas gun set-up with spherical projectiles at seven different pressure levels. Dispersion state of CNTs in the epoxy matrix systems was investigated by transmission electron microscope (TEM). In addition, effect of interaction of MWCNTs with epoxy and fiber/matrix bonding were investigated using scanning electron microscope (SEM). Projected damage area after impact test was evaluated by ultrasonic c-scan. All results were compared with the control composites containing no MWCNTs.

2. Experimental

At first, NH₂-MWCNTs were mixed manually with SC-15 Part-A of epoxy resin as per calculated weight ratio. The mixture was then sonicated at room temperature for 1 hour at 35% amplitude and 20 second on/ off cycle pulse mode. To improve the dispersion of MWCNTs further, the sonicated mixture was then passed through a three-roll mill for three times at different pre-selected gap settings. Roller speed of the three rolls was maintained at a ratio of 1:3:9 while a maximum speed of 180 rpm was maintained in all the three passes. The hardener, Part B was mixed as per stoichiometric ratio to the modified mixture with a mechanical stirrer for 10 minutes at 800 rpm. E-glass/epoxy nanocomposites were fabricated by using a combination of hand lay-up and hot press techniques to ensure proper fiber wetting and uniform resin distribution in the fabrics. Twelve layers of E-glass fabric were stacked properly. The entire setup was kept in a hot press at 60°C temperature and 1.43 MPa pressure for 6 hours. After completion of curing, the laminate was thermally post cured at 100°C for 5 hours without any pressure. The final thickness of the panel was found to be 5.25 mm.

3. Characterization

High velocity or ballistic impact tests were carried out using a gas-gun test set up. The gas gun consists of a 3 m long barrel, a fast acting high pressure firing valve, and capture chamber. The sample of dimension 120 mm x 120 mm x 5.25 mm was mounted in a fully clamped boundary condition between two rigid aluminum plates in the capture chamber. Spherical steel projectiles with a diameter of 7.90 mm and weighing 2.10gm were used. Polyurethane sabots assisted spherical projectiles through the barrel. The projectile was separated from the launching sabot by a sabot stripper plate before impacting the target. Initial velocity and residual velocity of the projectile

were measured using two chronographs mounted at the bottom of the capture chamber with a transparent optical window. Helium gas was used as propellant. Impact velocity was varied by varying the pressure of gas in the firing chamber. Seven different pressures setting varying from 0.34-1.38 MPa (50-200 psi) were used for the test. Incident velocity levels ranged from 240 m/s to 380 m/s and accordingly initial kinetic energy levels ranging from 60 J to 150 J. Dispersion states of MWCNTs in epoxy resin was investigated by Zeiss EM10 Transmission Electron Microscope operated at 60kV. The analysis of fracture surfaces was carried out using a Zeiss EVO50 scanning electron microscope (SEM) at 20 kV accelerating voltage. Specimen surfaces were coated with a thin gold film to protect the fracture surfaces from beam damage and to prevent charge build up. An Ultrasonic C-scan inspection was carried out to obtain quantitative information of damage of the impacted laminates using an ultrasonic pulse-receiver unit with ODIS software made by Sonix Inc. The scanning was carried out in pulse-echo immersion mode using a 5-MHz 50 mm point focus transducer. Scanning was done in the x-y direction with an electronic gate set on the back surface signal. Scan data was collected at every 0.05 mm interval. Software associated with the set-up has a provision to see real-time digitized oscilloscope where the signals are monitored. Both amplitude as well as time-of-flight information was collected and stored as image files in TIF or GIF format.

3. Results

3.1. High velocity impact characterization

3.1.1. Absorbed energy

High velocity impact properties were analyzed in terms of absorbed energy efficiency and ballistic limit velocity of fabricated laminates to figure out the effect of NH₂-MWCNTs on ballistic properties of E-glass/epoxy composites. Typical room temperature initial and final velocity determined by chronographs equipped in the testing device, are shown in Table. 1. The

summary of the calculated absorbed energy results at all of the impact velocity levels is shown in Table 2. Table 2 also provides the information on the projected damage calculated based on the ultrasonic c-scan images. For this calculation, damage is assumed to be elliptical in shape. Major and minor axes were measured to calculate the area. Numbers in the parenthesis give the percentage change in the damage area for samples with NH₂-MWCNTs as compared with control (ones with no NH₂-MWCNTs) samples.

Absorbed energy is one of the main parameters to assess and evaluate the degree of damage and process in a composite laminates after an impact incident. Impact energy is defined as the kinetic energy of the projectile that is transferred to composites just before impact while absorbed energy is the amount of energy dissipated within composites at the end of an impact event. Absorbed energy can be calculated in several ways. One of the ways is to measure the integral area under load-deflection curve which is treated as the total absorbed energy by a composite specimen. In this study, total absorbed energy was determined by the difference of initial kinetic energy just before impact and final kinetic energy just after impact according to equation (1).

$$E_a = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 - \frac{1}{2}mu^2 \quad (1)$$

where, m, v, and u are the mass, incident impact velocity and residual velocity of the projectile, respectively and E_a is the absorbed energy by the target.

The positive effect of NH₂-MWCNTs in epoxy resin is clearly evident in case of absorbed energy improvements (Table 2). Energy absorption capability by composites has been improved at 3 wt. % loading of CNTs with respect to control laminates and then decreased. As shown in Table 2, the results clearly show that, in some cases absorbed energy is lower than impact energy and in some cases absorbed

energy is same as impact energy. So some of the test data are below equal energy line where absorbed energy equals to impact energy and in other cases it is coincident on the line. This clearly indicates that there are complete penetrations in all the samples in which absorbed energy is less than impact energy. The excess energy i.e. impact energy minus absorbed energy, defined as residual energy was retained by the projectile after completely penetrating the sample. The other case indicates that the projectile is caught by the laminates and the projectile velocity becomes zero before all the fibers are broken. It indicates the absorbed energy and impact energy is same and the partial penetration has occurred.

3.1.2. Ultrasonic evaluation of impact damage

All the samples were subjected to ultrasonic c-scan evaluation after the impact tests to determine the extent of damage and correlate the incident impact energy to the damage. The tests were carried out in an immersion mode by pulse-echo technique. In this system the specimen was submerged into a water tank. An ultrasonic pulse was sent from the submerged piezoelectric transducer into the specimen. Ultrasonic pulse travels through the water column. Part of the signal gets reflected back from the front surface of the sample while remaining in transmitted into the sample. The portion of the pulse that is traveling through the sample will undergo inherent attenuation within the sample. If the location of the sample where ultrasonic pulse enters the sample is defect-free, the pulse travels through the thickness of the sample and again gets reflected back. On the other hand, if there is a defect or damage in the path of ultrasonic pulse, then that acts as a reflector and ultrasonic pulse gets reflected back from defect or damage. If the defect or damage is substantial, then most of the transmitted pulse will not reach the back surface. Collecting the back surface signal, hence from all the scanned points and converting the digitized data in an

image form will create a c-scan, which gives the projected information of the damage in the sample. Projected damage calculated based on the c-scan time-of-flight data is presented in the last column of Table 2. If the impact energy is less, the projectile bounces off the sample. However, in the current study, the lowest incident energy was high enough to create damage in the sample and projectiles actually penetrated the samples either partially or completely. When there is partial penetration, the projectile gets caught in the sample transferring its energy completely to the sample. Some of the incident energy of the sample is absorbed in elastic deformation of the sample while the remaining is spent in creating damage in the sample. Major mode of damage in woven fabric composites is delamination, in addition to fiber breakage at the back surface as well as matrix cracking as shown in Fig. 1. In general, the interface where the projectile gets arrested has the largest delamination. On the other hand, when the projectile completely penetrates the sample, the damage gets much more localized and is generally lower than the case where there is partial penetration of the sample. When the samples with MWCNTs are compared with those without MWCNTs on one-on-one basis at a given pressure setting, it is generally noticed that the damage size is much lower in case of samples with MWCNTs as can be seen from Figs. 2-3 which give front and back surface images as well as time-of-flight c-scan images of samples tested at 0.34 and 1.38 MPa pressure settings, respectively. This is more so when there is partial penetration, i.e. below the ballistic limit. This is due to the fact that the samples with MWCNTs have higher bending stiffness and absorb more energy in terms of elastic deformation than that of the control samples. Hence, the amount of energy that is required to create damage is relatively more. This results in lower damage area. Even after complete penetration, the damage area is less for samples with MWCNTs.

3.1.3. Effect of MWCNTs on ballistic properties and damage area

As previously stated, GFRP composites are considered as high-ductility advanced composites where possible damage mechanism by high velocity impacts are tensile failure and deformation of fiber yarns, delamination and matrix cracking [10]. In other word, these are the main energy absorbing mechanisms by GFRP composites. So, ballistic properties and damage mechanisms of the composites are strongly dependent on the fracture toughness and bending properties of the target including elastic modulus, tensile strength and failure strain of fiber and matrix as well as interfacial bonding between them.

One of the obvious factors that contribute to the improvements in ballistic impact properties is the increased load transfer capability between the epoxy matrix and nanotubes. It has been reported that effective stress transfer between epoxy matrix and amino-functionalized MWCNTs contributed in enhancing mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites [17]. However, an effective stress transfer between epoxy and nanotubes is strongly dependent on improved dispersion. Figure 4 shows the degree of dispersion at both of the loading that reveals clearly a better dispersion of 0.3 wt. % CNTs in epoxy resin. An improved dispersion of CNTs in matrix facilitates to enhance interfacial reactions and forms covalent bond between them. This covalent bond induces different cross-linking region into the epoxy matrix. Generally after mixing epoxy Part A and NH₂-MWCNTs, the interfacial reaction takes place between amine functional groups of MWCNTs and epoxide groups of DGEBA resin. Two ring opening reactions followed by a cross-linking reaction create interlocking structure in the resin blend which facilitates impediment of the mobility of polymer chains in the system [5]. A bridging between epoxy matrix and MWCNTs, and thus, a better adhesion between them has been observed due to crosslink interaction [18].

When crack propagates in nanocomposites through a nanotube, crack tips cannot break the strong MWCNTs due to the bridging by crosslinking. The energy of the tips is significantly reduced by the large quantity of nanotubes pullout. As a result, crack tips are then forced to stop or frequently change their crack propagation line. Due to this phenomenon, crack initiation and propagation become difficult within the matrix and at fiber-matrix inter-phase than that of without reinforced CNTs samples that result in a higher energy absorption capability in the composites. In addition, presence of epoxy silanes on the surface of E-glass fiber may react with amine groups of MWCNTs as well as with amine groups of epoxy systems. This chemical reactivity may have formed a strong covalent bond that has resisted the crack propagation and increased the interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix due to increased fracture toughness as shown in Fig. 5(b). It might be one of the reasons to have less delamination and matrix cracking that result in a decrease in damage area as well as an increase in absorption capability and ballistic limit of GFRP composites. However, no such bonding was observed in control GFRP samples as shown in Fig. 5(a).

The noticeable increase in absorbed energy, ballistic limit and projected damage area at 0.3 wt. % loading thus can be attributed to the better dispersion of MWCNTs and better interfacial interaction among the amino functionalized MWCNTs, epoxy matrix and epoxy silanes of glass fiber interfaces. A decrease in the ballistic performance of samples with 0.5 wt. % MWCNTs was observed. It is well known that high surface area of nanotubes gives it desirable interface to transfer stresses. However, it creates a strong attractive force between them leading to excessive CNTs agglomeration. In addition, incorporation of nanotubes in polymer matrix has a major influence on the viscosity of nanocomposites and hence, mechanical properties also. It was reported that the

incorporation of more than 0.3 wt. % loading increases the viscosity of matrix which is reported as an impediment to dispersion [5]. A poor dispersion has also been observed in case of 0.5 wt. % CNTs loading from the TEM investigation (Fig. 4-b). High viscosity increases the surface tension of resin systems. In case of laminate fabrication, this is one of the main problems as it causes poor wetting of the glass fibers that leads to poor adhesion between glass fibers and epoxy matrix during fabrication. As a result, a potential decrease has been observed in the ballistic limit velocity, absorbed energy and projected damage area of the composites at 0.5 wt. % loading.

4. Conclusions

In this study, NH₂-MWCNTs were incorporated in E-glass/epoxy composites to enhance ballistic impact performance. MWCNTs incorporation to the epoxy resin system was carried out through a combination of sonication and three-roll mill methods. Based on the experimental analysis, it can be reported that the addition of MWCNTs at 0.3 wt. % loading increased energy absorption capability and the damage tolerance considerably, exhibiting lower damage size. Amino-functionalized MWCNTs interact with epoxy system and epoxy silanes onto fiber surfaces create a higher cross-link density of polymer network. Modification of epoxy matrix and improved fiber-matrix interfacial shear strength might increase the fracture toughness. Overall, this work showed that the ballistic performance of E-glass/epoxy samples can be enhanced by adding a very small percentage of amino-functionalized MWCNTs. At higher loading, the effect is reduced due to poor dispersion that causes a poor interfacial interaction between fiber and matrix as well as due to increased viscosity that does not provide proper wetting of fibers and hence, the interfacial shear properties along with other mechanical properties are not enhanced.

References

- [1] M. Grujicic, W.C.Bell, L.L. Thompson, K.L. Koudela and B.A. Cheeseman. "Ballistic-protection performance of carbon-nanotube-doped poly-vinyl-ester-epoxy matrix composite armor reinforced with E-glass fiber mats" *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, Vol. 479, pp 10-22, 2008.
- [2] L.S. Schadler, S.C. Giannaris and P.M. Ajayan. "Load transfer in carbon nanotube epoxy composites" *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 73, pp 3842-3844, 1998.
- [3] F.H. Gojny, M. Wichmann, B. Fiedler and K. Schulte. "Influence of different carbon nanotubes on the mechanical properties of epoxy matrix composites-A comparative study" *Compos Sci. Technol.*, Vol. 65, pp 2300-13, 2005.
- [4] Y.H. Liao, M.T. Olivier, Z.Y. Liang, C. Zhang and B. Wang. "Investigation of the dispersion process of SWNTs/SC-15 epoxy resin nanocomposites" *Mater. Sci. Eng.A*, Vol. 385, pp 175-181, 2004.
- [5] M.M. Rahman, S. Zainuddin, M. Hosur, J.E. Malone, M.B.A. Salam, A. Kumar and S. Jeelani. "Improvements in mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties of e-glass/epoxy composites using amino-functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes" *Composite Structures*, Vol. 94, pp 2397-2406, 2012.
- [6] Y.S. Song and J.R. Youn. "Influence of dispersion rates of carbon nanotubes on physical properties of epoxy nanocomposites" *Carbon*, Vol. 43, pp1378-85, 2005.
- [7] N.G. Sahoo, S. Rana, J.W. Cho, L. Li and S.H. Chan. "Polymer nanocomposites based on functionalized carbon nanotubes." *Prog. Polym. Sci.* Vol. 35, pp 837-67, 2010.
- [8] Z. Yaping, Z. Aibo, C. Quinghua, Z. Jiaoxia and N. Rongchang. "Functionalized effect on carbon nanotube/epoxy nano-composites." *Mater Sci Eng A*, Vol. 435-436, pp 145-9, 2006.
- [9] P.C. Ma, S.Y. Mo, B.Z. Tang and J.K. Kim. "Dispersion, interfacial interaction and reagglomeration of functionalized carbon nanotubes in epoxy composites." *Carbon*, Vol. 48, pp. 1824-34, 2010.
- [10] N.K. Naik and P. Shirrao. "Composite structures under ballistic impact." *Compos. Struct.* Vol. 66, pp 579-90, 2004.
- [11] W.J. Cantwell and J. Morton. "Impact perforation of carbon fibre reinforced plastic" *Compos. Sci. Technol.* Vol. 38, No. 2, pp 119-41, 1990.
- [12] S.W.R. Lee and C.T. Sun. "Dynamic penetration of graphite/epoxy laminates impacted by a blunt-ended projectile." *Compos. Sci. Technol.* Vol. 49, No. 4, pp 369-80, 1993.

- [13] S.T. Jenq, H.S. Jing and C. Chung. "Predicting the ballistic limit for plain woven glass/epoxy composite laminate." *Int. J. Impact Eng.* Vol. 15, pp 451-64, 1994.
- [14] C. Ulven, U.K. Vaidya and M.V. Hosur. "Effect of projectile shape during ballistic perforation of VARTM carbon/epoxy composite panels." *Compos. Struct.* Vol. 61, pp143-150, 2003.
- [15] J.M. Esfahani, A.R. Sabet and M. Esfandeh. "Assessment of nanocomposites based on unsaturated polyester resin/nanoclay under impact loading." *Polym. Adv. Techno.* Vol. 23, No. 4, pp 817-24, 2012.
- [16] A.F. Ávila, A.S. Neto and J.H. Nascimento. "Hybrid nanocomposites for midrange ballistic protection." *Int J Impact Eng* Vol. 38, No. 8, pp 669-76, 2011.
- [17] J. Shen, W. Huang, L. Wu, Y. Hu and M. Ye. "Thermo-physical properties of epoxy nanocomposites reinforced with amino-functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes." *Compos Part A*, Vol. 38, pp 1331–1336, 2007.

Figure 1. Optical microscope of fractured samples showing (a) fiber-matrix delamination and (b) fiber breakage

Figure 2. Pictures of top and bottom surface, and ultrasonic time-of-flight c-scan images showing projected damage of samples tested at 1.38 MPa pressure setting

Figure 3. Pictures of top and bottom surface, and ultrasonic time-of-flight c-scan images showing projected damage of samples tested at 0.34 MPa pressure setting.

Fig.4. TEM micrographs of a) 0.3 wt. %, and, b) 0.5 wt. % loading of NH₂-MWCNTs in epoxy resin.

Figure 5. Interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix in (a) neat sample and in (b) 0.3 wt. % CNTs incorporated sample.

**HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT RESONONSE OF E-GLASS/EPOXY
COMPOSITES MODIFIED WITH NH₂-MWNCT**

Table 1. Ballistic impact results of control and NH₂-MWCNTs incorporated E-glass/epoxy composites

Sample	Specimen no.	Incident velocity (m/s)	Residual velocity (m/s)	Remarks
Control GFRP	01	367.38	189.63	P
	02	332.01	115.85	P
	03	324.08	76.52	P
	04	309.75	71.03	P
	05	299.08	9.45	P
	06	290.85	0.00	E
	07	264.32	0.00	E
0.3 wt. % CNT-doped GFRP	01	369.82	185.97	P
	02	335.06	89.02	P
	03	319.51	18.90	P
	04	306.70	5.18	P
	05	301.82	0.00	E
	06	291.16	0.00	E
	07	269.51	0.00	E
0.5 wt. % CNT-doped GFRP	01	369.82	201.83	P
	02	331.70	117.98	P
	03	329.26	108.84	P
	04	319.82	74.39	P
	05	300.91	0.00	E
	06	283.23	0.00	E
	07	248.17	0.00	E

P=Penetration, E= Embedded

Table 2. Calculated initial kinetic energy, residual kinetic energy, absorbed energy and projected damage area of control and CNT-incorporated E-glass/epoxy composites

Sample	Specimen no.	Absorbed energy, $U_k - U_r$ (J)	Projected Damage Area (cm^2)	% difference in damage area w.r.t. reference
Reference GFRP	01	103.95	40.32	-
	02	101.65	44.35	-
	03	104.13	48.38	-
	04	95.44	49.16	-
	05	93.83	56.45	-
	06	88.83	56.45	-
	07	73.36	49.39	-
0.3 wt. % CNT-doped GFRP	01	107.28	32.26	-19.99
	02	109.56	40.32	-9.07
	03	106.83	40.32	-16.67
	04	98.74	44.35	-9.78
	05	95.66	36.29	-35.71
	06	89.01	32.25	-42.87
	07	76.27	48.38	-2.04
0.5 wt. % CNT-doped GFRP	01	100.83	36.29	-9.99
	02	100.91	40.32	-9.07
	03	101.59	44.35	-8.33
	04	101.40	48.38	-1.59
	05	95.08	48.38	-14.30
	06	84.23	40.32	-28.58
	07	64.66	48.38	-2.04